

EDAP+ TN on Quality Assessment of ICEYE InSAR and ScanSAR

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document describes the quality assessment of ICEYE's InSAR (Interferometric SAR) and Scan (ScanSAR) data products. ICEYE is an X-band SAR satellite constellation formed by many relatively small satellites. Over 30 satellites have been launched by ICEYE since 2018, and at least 20 more are planned to be launched during 2024 and beyond [RD-1]. This makes ICEYE the world's largest currently available spaceborne SAR constellation. The constellation enables imaging of specified areas of interest multiple times a day, allowing quick tactical acquisitions as well as frequent revisit rates globally. The newer ICEYE satellites include improvements compared to the older ones.

The quality assessment described in this document is performed following the SAR specific EDAP+ assessment guidelines [RD-2]. Products related to the InSAR data assessment have been collected with ICEYE's X6 satellite, that was launched on the 28th of September 2020 with the Soyuz-2-1v rocket from Plesetsk, Russia. X6 was the only satellite available for interferometry at the time of this activity. The assessed Scan products have been acquired with the 2nd generation X8, X12 and X13 satellites. X8 was launched on the 24th of January 2021, while X11 and X13 on the 30th of June 2021, all on board the Facon 9 rocket of SpaceX, from Cape Canaveral, Florida.

The quality assessment is divided into two main parts: Documentation review and an analysis of the test datasets. The document review in Chapter 2 includes the assessment of the documentation provided by ICEYE. The grading of these documents is given in columns 1-3 of the Summary Cal/Val Maturity Matrix (Figure 1-1). Chapter 3 describes the data assessment performed by the EDAP+ team for the requested ICEYE test data over the validation sites. A generic grading for the data assessment is given in the last column of the Summary Cal/Val Maturity Matrix (Figure 1-1), and a more specific grading for the different quality parameters is given in the Validation Cal/Val Maturity Matrices (Figure 1-2 and Figure 1-3). Similar assessments have been previously performed on ICEYE's 1st generation X2-X7 [RD-3, RD-4] and 2nd generation X11-X13 [RD-5] satellites, for which the final reports are available in the European Space Agency (ESA) EDAP+ project web page.

The interactive documentation available online in the ICEYE webpages provided comprehensive information about SAR imaging in general, and details on the processing and characteristics of the available ICEYE products. The calibration-validation documentation shared by ICEYE with the EDAP+ team (not publicly available) [RD-6] provided additional information about the internal validation activities performed by ICEYE for the Strip and Spot data products. The online documentation corresponds to the traditional Product User Guide and ATBD. The documentation is continuously being updated, currently versions 5.0-5.2 are available. Older versions of the ICEYE documents in pdf-format [RD-7, RD-8] and a conference publication [RD-9] are also available online. In addition to the basic Level 1 SAR products, ICEYE offers higher level products and solutions in various topics, including flood monitoring, vessel detection, agriculture, ice chart mapping for sea navigation and oil spill detection. Documentation describing these analyses can be accessed upon registration through ICEYE's website.

All necessary and relevant details on the ICEYE products are publicly available in the online product documentation, previous versions of product documentation [RD-7, RD-8] and in a conference publication [RD-9]. The data is provided to the user in standard file formats, easily read and understood, such as HDF5, GeoTIFF and XML. The data can be easily accessed and processed also with the publicly available SNAP toolbox distributed by ESA. Data order and delivery to the customer was smooth due to well written and clear instructions regarding the FTP delivery procedures. Product metadata includes the relevant flags with the necessary information on the data products. Ancillary data used in product generation relevant for SAR are also specified in the metadata or product documentation. All relevant characteristics of the SAR sensor system and SAR system geometry are stated in the documentation and/or in the product metadata, but documentation about pre-flight calibration activities is minimal. The metrological traceability of the ICEYE products is not documented.

A general description of the post-launch radiometric and geometric calibration methods and activities, as well as the uncertainty characterization and quality assessment performed internally by ICEYE, is given in the online product documentation. A more detailed description of these, specifically for the Strip and Spot modes of the X11-X13 satellites, is given in a document provided to the EDAP+ team [RD-6]. All basic uncertainty values for SAR are thus provided, such as the spatial resolution, ISLR (Integrated Side Lobe Ratio), PSLR (Peak Side Lobe Ratio), NESZ (Noise Equivalent Sigma Zero) and geolocation accuracy. The given uncertainty values are based on analyses of several datasets. Single uncertainty values for each imaging mode are provided in the ICEYE web site and in the online interactive documentation. More detailed results for X11-X13 are presented in RD-6, but these cover only the Strip and Spot modes, and not the Scan mode. Pixel-wise uncertainty is not provided. The calibration algorithm and the geometric processing of the data products are well documented in the online documentation and in the additional document RD-6 provided to EDAP+ team. RD-10 is a document showing the results of ICEYE's internal InSAR quality assessment. The document was provided by ICEYE to the EDAP+ assessment team, and it is not publicly available. It demonstrates the performance of the X6 ICEYE data for InSAR applications when the SARPROZ software is used. A summary of these results is provided in Section 3.5.

An independent assessment of the essential quality parameters for SAR was performed by the EDAP+ team, using representative datasets acquired with the ICEYE satellites. The InSAR test dataset was acquired from the Atacama Desert area, South America. This is a stable and still target with bare and rough mountainous terrain and salt flats, which are well suitable for interferometric SAR analyses, due to their high interferometric coherence. The assessed data included 5 new image stacks of the Spot imaging mode, and 5 (4 new and 1 archive) image stacks of the Strip imaging mode, all of them Single Look Complex (SLC) data products. Each stack included 4 scenes, acquired with 1-2 days interval (temporal baseline). The InSAR data assessment was done with the SNAP software. The assessed InSAR parameters include the spatial baseline, the differences in Doppler centroids, and the coherences calculated from the interferometric pairs.

The evaluated Scan data included 99 Ground Range Detected (GRD) products, collected from various test sites. These enabled a comprehensive assessment of the most relevant SAR quality parameters, such as the spatial resolution, PSLR, ISLR, geolocation accuracy, equivalent number of looks (ENL), NESZ, antenna elevation pattern (AEP), radiometric artifacts related to azimuth scalloping and inter-swath boundaries (ISB), and radiometric stability. All ICEYE data are in VV-polarization (single-polarization), with incidence angles ranging between 15 and 35 degrees. The measured quality parameters in our analyses were compared with the corresponding values stated in ICEYE's documentation. In case the quality values were not provided in the ICEYE documentation, the quality parameters were assessed based on commonly known SAR data quality.

Before calculating the coherence, coregistration of the interferometric pair is required. In the coregistration, the secondary image is spatially aligned with the primary image, for attaining the best possible overlap between the images. The coregistration in SNAP succeeded for most of the Strip data pairs, but only for one Spot pair. For improving the coregistration results we also tried DEM-assisted coregistration with Xcorr, using the TanDEM-X 12 m resolution DEM, and tested different parameter configurations for the coregistration. However, the gained improvements were only limited, and many times the recommended method by ICEYE produced an error in SNAP. We suspect that the major reason for the problems in coregistration was large spatial shifts between the image pairs. After coregistration, the interferometric coherence of the image pairs was calculated. As expected, the coherence was usually better over the salt flats than in the surrounding arid plateaus or dry and rocky slopes. However, in general, the coherence was found to be lower than expected for the test areas. Only for two Strip pairs the coherence could be considered reasonable, namely around 0.7 over the salt flats. For the rest of the data, the coherence was considered too low, meaning around 0.4 or less for targets that should have had high coherences. The perpendicular baseline (B_p) was typically few hundred meters, which is considered suitable for interferometry. The Doppler centroid (DC) anomalies were usually between 100 and 700 Hz for the Spot scenes, and between 20 and 180 Hz for the Strip scenes. We noticed that pairs with exceptionally large B_p and/or DC anomalies led to errors in coregistration or to lower coherences.

However, these factors were most likely not the only ones that caused coherence values lower than expected. The InSAR coherence results obtained by ICEYE with the SARPROZ software are significantly better than the results obtained by the EDAP+ team with the SNAP software for the same X6 data. This difference emphasizes the importance of the software choice. Especially for interferometric applications that require complex computations, it is crucial that the data are well compatible with the modules of the software. SARPROZ is dedicated to InSAR applications, and it is also the standard software choice for interferometric processing at ICEYE. However, it is less available for typical users. In contrary, SNAP is available for all users, but based on our InSAR quality assessment, it is currently less tailored to work with ICEYE InSAR data.

The validation of the Scan data was performed using the SAR Quality Toolbox (SQT) dedicated to the assessment of SAR data quality, developed by Aresys. There were few scenes delivered by ICEYE where the radiometric quality was low, and several scenes where the localization error was found large. Following a request of the EDAP+ team, these scenes were reprocessed by ICEYE, and their quality was usually improved.

The measured ENL for the analysed ICEYE data from Antarctica Glacier was close to the ideal value of one for all data, meaning correct radiometric signatures. The AEP correction performed by the data provider to the Scan data was found to be basic for all analysed satellites. Gamma Nought (γ^0) range profiles from the Amazonas had typically a change of 2-4 dB between near and far range. Only two out of the analysed 24 scenes had profiles that could be considered as flat and stable. The scenes with incidence angles close to 30° had somewhat better range profiles than the ones with $\sim 20^\circ$ angle. The measured NESZ over the Desert surfaces was usually close to the expected values of -22.2 to -21.5 dB for the ICEYE Scan mode, but over the Doldrums water surfaces it was many times higher than the expected level. The measured stronger NESZ values can be related to an overestimation of the SQT compared to the values measured by ICEYE, due to differences in the methodologies for NESZ estimation. Also, some of the Doldrums images had wavy water surfaces that increase the backscatter. Finding very low backscatter test areas was challenging, because all data are co-polarization (not cross-polarization) and the maximum incidence angle is only around 30° .

Azimuth scalloping and ISB periodic noise artifacts were assessed by visually inspecting the backscatter images from Glacier and Amazonas and the range profiles of the AEP analysis from the Amazonas. Quite strong azimuth scalloping artifacts were present in most of the Glacier images, and weaker scalloping artifacts over the Amazonas. Usually there were no ISB artifacts, or they were very weak. Only in a few images the ISB artifacts appeared clearly. For the Rainforest images, periodic noise was the strongest for X8 and the weakest for X13, but in Glacier all analysed satellites showed similar quality. Weaker ISB artifacts compared to the azimuth scalloping were expected, as ICEYE are applying the TOPSAR (Terrain Observation with Progressive Scans) technique for avoiding ISB artifacts, but radiometric corrections for compensating the scalloping noise are not implemented. In 15 out of the 24 analysed scenes from the Amazonas the average backscatter was between -8.5 and -6.5 dB. However, in 9 scenes the backscatter was notably weaker, namely between -14 and -9 dB. The standard deviation within the scenes was usually between 1 to 2 dB, with a few exceptions of larger variability. Therefore, the radiometric stability in ICEYE Scan data was found to be basic.

The measured quality parameters in the IRF analysis performed over the Rosamond corner reflector (CR) site were partially in line with the values provided by ICEYE. Concerning spatial resolution, the measured values were always better than the values provided in the ICEYE documentation. Concerning side lobes, in azimuth direction the results were in accordance with the reported values, but in range direction the side lobes were relatively strong. All analysed satellites had similar performance concerning spatial resolution and side lobes. Compared to other X-band SAR data providers, the ICEYE products have generally higher spatial resolution, but also relatively high side lobes. This is because no smoothing window function (e.g. Taylor, Hanning, Hamming or Kaiser) is applied by ICEYE during data processing. The localization errors measured over the CRs were in accordance with the reported values for X8, but for X12 and X13 the errors were notably larger than expected. Also, for X8 the errors were usually larger in range than in azimuth, while for X12 and X13 the errors were larger in azimuth.

1.1 References

The following is a list of reference documents with a direct bearing on the content of this proposal. Where referenced in the text, these are identified as [RD-n], where 'n' is the number in the list below:

RD-1. ICEYE brochure Q3 2024: Accurate, near real-time Earth monitoring with SAR data. Available online: https://www.iceye.com/hubfs/Downloadables/SAR_Data_Brochure_ICEYE.pdf (10/2024)

RD-2. EDAP Best Practice Guidelines: Technical Note on Methods and Reference Data for SAR Data Quality Assessments, EDAP+.REP.007, v1.1, May 2023. Available online: <https://earth.esa.int/eogateway/activities/edap/sar-missions> (07/2024)

RD-3. ICEYE X2 Quality Assessment Summary, EDAP report. Available online: <https://earth.esa.int/eogateway/activities/edap/sar-missions> (07/2024)

RD-4. ICEYE X4, X6 and X7 Quality Assessment Summary, EDAP report. Available online: <https://earth.esa.int/eogateway/activities/edap/sar-missions> (07/2024)

RD-5. ICEYE X11, X12 and X13 Quality Assessment Summary, EDAP report. Available online: <https://earth.esa.int/eogateway/activities/edap/sar-missions> (07/2024)

RD-6. SAR Calibration and Performance Verification for X11-X13 satellites, 2023, ICEYE

RD-7. SAR Product Guide, Version 3.0. released in 01.05.2020, ICEYE

RD-8. Data Calibration and Validation, version 1.0, released 22/6/2020, ICEYE

RD-9. V. Ignatenko, P. Laurila, A. Radius, L. Lamentowski, O. Antropov and D. Muff, "ICEYE Microsatellite SAR Constellation Status Update: Evaluation of First Commercial Imaging Modes," *IGARSS 2020 - 2020 IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium*, Waikoloa, HI, USA, 2020, pp. 3581-3584, doi: 10.1109/IGARSS39084.2020.9324531.

RD-10. InSAR Quality Assessment – ICEYE datasets, 31.10.2024, ICEYE

RD-11. M. C. Garthwaite, M. Hazelwood, S. Nancarrow, A. Hislop & J. H. Dawson (2015) A regional geodetic network to monitor ground surface response to resource extraction in the northern Surat Basin, Queensland, Australian Journal of Earth Sciences, 62:4, 469-477, DOI: 10.1080/08120099.2015.1040073

1.2 Glossary

The following acronyms and abbreviations have been used in this Report.

AEP	Antenna Elevation Pattern
ALE	Absolute Localization Error
ATBD	Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document
B	Interferometric Baseline
Bc	Critical Baseline
Bp	Perpendicular Baseline
CR	Corner Reflector
DC	Doppler Centroid
DEM	Digital Elevation Model
EDAP	Earthnet Data Assessment Project
ENL	Equivalent Number Looks
ESA	European Space Agency
FTP	File Transfer Protocol
GRD	Ground Range Detected
InSAR	Interferometric SAR
ISB	Inter-Swath Boundaries
ISLR	Integrated Side Lobe Ratio
LoS	Line of Sight
NESZ	Noise Equivalent Sigma Zero
PSLR	Peak Side Lobe Ratio
RD	Reference Document
SAR	Synthetic Aperture Radar
SLC	Single Look Complex
SNAP	SeNtinel Application Platform
SQT	SAR Quality Toolbox
TOPSAR	Terrain Observation with Progressive Scans

1.3 Cal/Val Maturity Matrices

1.3.1 Summary Cal/Val Maturity Matrix

Data Provider Documentation Review			Validation Summary	Key	
Product Information	Metrology	Product Generation		Not Assessed	Not Assessable
Product Details	Sensor Calibration & Characterisation	Calibration Algorithm	Scan Measurement Validation Method	Basic	
Availability & Accessibility	Geometric Calibration & Characterisation	Geometric Processing	Scan Measurement Validation Results Compliance	Good	
Product Format, Flags & Metadata	Metrological Traceability Documentation	Mission-Specific Processing	Scan Geometric Validation Method	Excellent	
User Documentation	Uncertainty Characterisation Not Public				
	Ancillary Data		InSAR Validation Method		
			InSAR Validation Results Compliance		

Figure 1-1: Summary Cal/Val Maturity Matrix for the analysed ICEYE satellites

1.3.2 Validation Cal/Val Maturity Matrix

FMI Detailed Validation				Key
Measurement		Geometric		
Interferometric Coherence Method	Interferometric Coherence Results Compliance	Perpendicular Baseline Method	Perpendicular Baseline Results Compliance	Not Assessed
		Doppler Centroid Method	Doppler Centroid Results Compliance	Not Assessable
				Basic
				Good
				Excellent
				Ideal
				🔒 Not Public

Figure 1-2: Validation Cal/Val Maturity Matrix for the InSAR quality parameters of the ICEYE X6 satellite.

FMI Detailed Validation				Key
Measurement		Geometric		
NESZ Method	NESZ Results Compliance	Geolocation Error Method	Geolocation Error Results Compliance	Not Assessed
ENL Method	ENL Results Compliance	Spatial Resolution Method	Spatial Resolution Results Compliance	Not Assessable
AEP Method	AEP Results Compliance	PSLR Method	PSLR Results Compliance	Basic
Stability Method	Stability Results Compliance	ISLR Method	ISLR Results Compliance	Good
Scalloping & ISB Method	Scalloping & ISB Results Compliance			Excellent
				Ideal
				🔒 Not Public

Figure 1-3: Validation Cal/Val Maturity Matrix for the Scan imaging mode of the ICEYE X8, X12 and X13 satellites.

2. DATA PROVIDER DOCUMENTATION REVIEW

2.1 Product Information

Product Details	
Grade: Excellent	
Justification	All necessary product details are provided in the online product documentation, older versions of documents in pdf-format, and/or in a conference publication [RD-9]. Radiometric accuracy is provided only in the older documentation and the conference publication.
Product Name	ICEYE_[sat. number]_[PL]_[im.mode]_[id]_YYYYMMDDTHHmss, where [sat. number] is the number of the ICEYE satellite, e.g. X8. [PL] is the processing level of the product; SLC or GRD. [im. mode] is the imaging mode; SC for ScanSAR, SM for Stripmap, SL for Spotlight and SLH for Spotlight High. [id] is the product identification number. YYYYMMDD and HHmss are the acquisition start date and time.
Sensor Name	X6, X8, X12 and X13 were evaluated; X6 related to InSAR, and X8, X12 and X13 related to ScanSAR assessment.
Sensor Type	X-band SAR
Mission Type	Constellation – 4 satellites out of the constellation are evaluated
Mission Orbit	Sun Synchronous Polar Orbit
Product Version Number	The evaluated products are of processor versions 1.88-1.91 for the X8, X12 and X13 Scan data and 1.92-1.99 for the X6 InSAR data.
Product ID	A number with up to seven digits individual for each product
Processing level of product	Level 1 SLC of X6 and Level 1 GRD of X8, X12 and X13 were evaluated
Measured Quantity Name	Radar Backscatter
Measured Quantity Units	dB
Stated Measurement Quality	Absolute radiometric accuracy, namely the RMSE between measured and true RCS, is estimated < 2 dB. Relative radiometric accuracy, namely the standard deviation of the radiometric error of known targets within one data take, is estimated < 1 dB.
Spatial Resolution	Spot, Strip and Scan acquisition modes are evaluated. The spatial resolution (range x azimuth) for these modes are: Scan: 15 x 15 (GRD) Strip: 0.5-2.5 x 3 (SLC) Spot: 0.5 x 0.25 (SLC)
Spatial Coverage	Size of one standard scene (swath width x length) Scan: 100 x 100 Strip: 30 x 50 Spot: 5 x 5
Temporal Resolution	Daily repeat pass for selected targets (not yet global)
Temporal Coverage	Constellation mean revisit time at the equator is 20 hours. Constellation mean time to access at equator is 12 hours.

Point of Contact	<i>customer@iceye.com</i>
Product locator (DOI/URL)	<i>NA</i>
Conditions for access and use	<i>Data were provided under specific agreement for utilization within the EDAP+ framework.</i>
Limitations on public access	<i>Data not publicly accessible</i>
Product Abstract	<i>NA</i>

Availability & Accessibility	
Grade: Excellent	
Justification	<i>Most of the Fair principles met, except: Metadata and data include qualified references to other (meta)data.</i>
Compliant with FAIR principles	<i>Mostly yes</i>
Data Management Plan	<i>Standard orders are submitted by filling out a Standard Order Form with required information on requested datasets, via email for existing users and via sending an email to the customer service for new customers. Custom orders with a higher level of flexibility are initiated by submitting a Custom Order Form via the email for existing customers, and by contacting the ICEYE sales team through ICEYE website for new customers. Archive imagery orders can be submitted via email. Access to the public archive of ICEYE radar preview imagery is possible after registration. The available archive scenes can be previewed e.g. in Google Earth, QGIS or other common GIS-software.</i>
Availability Status	<i>Standard orders are delivered via SFTP server to the customer within 12 hours after the data is acquired. Faster delivery of only a few hours is possible for urgent requests. Archive scenes are delivered up to 12 hours after an order is received. It is possible to use free software (e.g. SNAP) for data processing and analysis.</i>

Product Format	
Grade: Excellent	
Justification	<i>Data provided in standard file formats. Relevant flags included, such as flags indicating if antenna elevation pattern and free space loss compensation, and windowing function were applied. Metadata includes all necessary information on the data products.</i>
Product File Format	<i>HDF5 and XML for SLC data GeoTIFF and XML for GRD data PNG and KML for quicklook images</i>
Metadata Conventions	<i>HDF, XML</i>
Analysis Ready Data?	<i>No</i>

User Documentation		
Grade: Excellent		
Justification	<p>An online interactive product documentation is provided in the ICEYE webpages. This includes comprehensive information about the products, corresponding to the traditional Product User Guide and ATBD. Downloadable product documentation (pdf-versions) include the “SAR data brochure”, which provide basic information on the data products and quality, and older versions of documentation. The online documentation is continuously being updated, currently versions 5.0-5.2 available.</p>	
<i>Document</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>QA4ECV Compliant</i>
Product User Guide	ICEYE online product documentation	no
ATBD	ICEYE online product documentation	no

2.2 Metrology

Sensor Calibration & Characterisation	
Grade: Good	
Justification	<p>All relevant characteristics of the SAR sensor system are stated in the documentation and/or in the product metadata. Documentation about pre-flight calibration activities is minimal. A general description of the post-launch radiometric (sensor) calibration methods and activities is given in the online product documentation. A more detailed description of the calibration and validation activities for the X11-X13 satellites is given in RD-6, although these are provided only for the Strip and Spot imaging modes, not for Scan. The radiometric calibration by ICEYE was performed using homogeneous targets and point targets. It included e.g. antenna elevation beam calibration and calibration coefficient calculation. Calibration against homogeneous targets was initially performed over Amazon rainforest, and a validation of the calibration parameters was done using Congo rainforest data. The corner reflectors in Rosamond JPL site were used in the radiometric calibration against point targets. The calibration parameters were derived through an analysis of many images. Routine and ongoing validation activities are planned for the operational ICEYE satellites.</p>
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ICEYE online product documentation • RD-6

Geometric Calibration & Characterisation	
Grade: Good	
Justification	<p>All relevant characteristics of the SAR system geometry are stated in the documentation and/or in the product metadata. Documentation about pre-flight geometric calibration activities is minimal. A general description of the post-launch geometric calibration methods and activities is given in the online product documentation. A more detailed description of the calibration and validation activities for the X11-X13 satellites is given in RD-6, although these are provided only for the Strip and Spot imaging modes, not for Scan. The geometric calibration and verification by ICEYE was performed using point target calibration sites around the world, specifically the NASA JPL corner reflector array in Rosamond, California. The calibration parameters were evaluated through an analysis of many images. Routine and ongoing validation activities are planned for the operational ICEYE satellites.</p>
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ICEYE online product documentation • RD-6

Metrological Traceability Documentation	
Grade: Not Assessable	

Justification	<i>Metrological traceability not documented</i>
References	NA

Uncertainty Characterisation	
Grade: Excellent	
Justification	<p><i>The methods and the results of the uncertainty characterization performed internally by ICEYE are well documented. A general description of the methods and results of the uncertainty characterisation and quality assessment is provided in the online documentation. A more detailed description concerning the X11-X13 satellites was provided in RD-6, although it covers only the Strip and Spot imaging modes, not Scan. The uncertainty characterisation includes the relevant quality indicators for SAR, such as an IRF analyses for the assessment of spatial resolution, side lobes and localization error, as well as radiometric validation, including NESZ, radiometric accuracy and AEP.</i></p> <p><i>All relevant uncertainty values for SAR are thus provided. The given uncertainty values are based on analyses of several datasets. Single uncertainty values for each imaging mode are provided in the ICEYE web site and in the online interactive documentation. A more detailed results for the Strip and Spot modes of X11-X13 are presented in RD-6. Pixel-wise uncertainty is not provided. Radiometric accuracy is provided only in the old versions of the product documentation.</i></p> <p><i>The InSAR performance for the X6 satellite data was assessed by ICEYE using the commercial SARPROZ software, for providing a reference to the analysis done by the EDAP+ team using the publicly available SNAP software. ICEYE analysed the same X6 datasets from the Atacama Desert areas that were assessed by the EDAP+ team. ICEYE's analysis included the coregistration of the interferometric pairs, followed by calculation of coherences and interferograms.</i></p>
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>ICEYE online product documentation</i> • <i>RD-6</i> • <i>RD-7</i> • <i>RD-9</i> • <i>RD-10</i>

Ancillary Data	
Grade: Good	
Justification	<i>Ancillary data used in product generation relevant for SAR are specified in the metadata or product documentation, such as the digital elevation model used, not on a per product basis.</i>
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>ICEYE online product documentation</i>

2.3 Product Generation

Calibration Algorithm	
Grade: Excellent	
Justification	<i>Calibration algorithm well documented. The SAR processor compensates for the effects of range spread loss, elevation antenna pattern, different azimuth and range bandwidths, and sensor settings variations (receiver gain, transmit power, duty cycle). Further calibration and validation activities are routinely performed for the ICEYE satellites [RD-6, RD-8]. Information about the performed calibration is provided in the metadata per product, such as the amplification factors for antenna elevation and free space loss compensation.</i>
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ICEYE online product documentation • RD-6 • RD-8

Geometric Processing	
Grade: Excellent	
Justification	<i>The geometric processing is well documented and all relevant calibration parameters are provided. In azimuth image pixels are always focused to the zero-Doppler. In range the processor applies path length corrections (typically on the order of a couple of metres) using well established models. An RPC model has been implemented for the determination of precise pixel locations. Timing corrections are applied to satellite internal clocks by periodically synchronising with GNSS. The satellite position and velocity state vectors are refined after the imaging operation using downlinked telemetry and attitude data. For amplitude scenes, a conversion from Beta Nought to Sigma Nought is applied using the incidence angle calculated from the ellipsoid model. The geolocation accuracy of the satellites is routinely verified by collecting and analysing images over ground-surveyed calibration sites containing calibration point targets such as trihedral corner reflectors.</i>
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ICEYE online product documentation • RD-6 • RD-8

Mission-Specific Processing	
Grade: Not Assessable	
Justification	<i>Additional processing steps are not documented.</i>
Reference	NA

3. DETAILED VALIDATION – INSAR

In interferometric SAR (InSAR) applications, the phase difference between two SAR acquisitions acquired with slightly different geometries are used to generate interferograms. These can be further processed and merged with other spatial data to discover ground elevation or deformations. The quality of the interferogram is affected by many factors, such as target properties, Doppler centroid differences, spatial and temporal baselines, and atmospheric effects. One of the main requirements for successful InSAR processing is a target having high interferometric correlation (coherence), i.e. it produces sufficient backscatter where the phase remains stable over time.

This chapter describes the assessment of the InSAR quality parameters performed by the EDAP+ team, using test datasets acquired with the ICEYE X6 satellite. At the time of this activity, X6 was the only satellite available for interferometric applications with suitable temporal baselines. The assessed InSAR quality parameters include the perpendicular and critical baselines, the difference in Doppler centroids, and interferometric coherence between the image pairs. For obtaining the best results, ICEYE recommends using the SARPROZ software (www.sarproz.com). SNAP software can also be used for processing the ICEYE data, but it may have sub-optimal results, as the co-registration algorithm is not sufficiently robust for the fine spatial resolution and longer spatial baselines as is the case of ICEYE data. Nevertheless, in our assessment we used the SNAP software, because it is open source and thus more available for potential users. The internal quality assessment of the X6 data performed by ICEYE using the recommended SARPROZ software is summarised in section 3.5, together with a comparison between the coherences obtained with SNAP and SARPROZ.

3.1 Introduction

ICEYE X6 SLC Strip and Spot data were collected from the Atacama Desert area over Chile, Argentina and Bolivia, in South America. The assessed data contains 5 stacks of 4 Spot scenes and 5 stacks of 4 Strip scenes. All Spot stacks and 4 Strip stacks contain new acquisitions acquired between July and Oct 2023. One of the Strip stacks contains archive scenes that were acquired in the beginning of June 2021. The stacks are hereafter named as “Strip 1” ... “Strip 4” for the new Strip stacks and “Strip Archive” for the archive Strip stack, and “Spot 1” ... “Spot 5” for the new Spot stacks. Figure 4 shows the location of the collected image stacks on top of a Google background map, and Table 1 provides information on the ID numbers and dates of the acquired scenes. The temporal baseline between the 1st and the 2nd, and between the 3rd and the 4th scene of the stacks was always one day. Two days separated between the 2nd and the 3rd scenes, except for the “Strip archive” stack that had one day interval, and “Spot 3” stack that had about 2 months temporal difference between the 2nd and the 3rd scene.

Figure 4: Location of the collected image stacks on top of Google Earth images.

The Atacama Desert area is located on the western slopes of the Andes Mountain ridge, mostly over Chile, Argentina, and Bolivia. The area contains mainly dry and rocky mountain slopes, arid desert plateaus, and dry salt flats in some of the valleys. The area is in general suitable for interferometric applications, due to the clear topographic shapes and temporal interferometric stability of the targets. Due to the high revisit time of the X6 satellite, the coverage was limited. All new images were chosen from one specific ascending right looking orbit that included the most salt flats, as these are specifically good for InSAR, due homogeneous and relatively high backscatter on top of the high temporal stability, leading to high interferometric coherences. Thus, target-wise, the area should provide high coherence values.

Table 1: The assessed ICEYE X6 data; stack names, scene IDs and the dates of the acquisitions. SM indicates Stripmap, SL Spotlight, and SLH Spotlight High imaging mode.

Stack	Scene ID	Date
Strip Archive	SM_58530	20210603
	SM_58531	20210604
	SM_59561	20210605
	SM_59564	20210606
Strip 1	SM_2351485	20230716
	SM_2351486	20230717
	SM_2351487	20230719
	SM_2351488	20230720
Strip 2	SM_2440324	20230802
	SM_2448045	20230803
	SM_2448046	20230805
	SM_2448047	20230806
Strip 3	SM_2490445	20230814
	SM_2507860	20230815
	SM_2507861	20230817
	SM_2513263	20230818
Strip 4	SM_2568244	20230826
	SM_2581920	20230827
	SM_2599459	20230829
	SM_2599460	20230830
Spot 1	SL_2450856	20230808
	SL_2450857	20230809
	SL_2480416	20230811
	SL_2490444	20230812
Spot 2	SLH_2333586	20230710
	SLH_2337462	20230711
	SLH_2337463	20230713
	SLH_2348668	20230714
Spot 3	SLH_2516428	20230820
	SLH_2516429	20230821
	SLH_2845583	20231015
	SLH_2856724	20231016
Spot 4	SLH_2352992	20230722
	SLH_2360400	20230723
	SLH_2401211	20230725
	SLH_2408987	20230726
Spot 5	SLH_2599461	20230901
	SLH_2602530	20230902
	SLH_2633501	20230904
	SLH_2635330	20230905

3.2 Baseline

The interferometric baseline (B) is the distance between the orbits of the InSAR satellite pair in a plane perpendicular to the satellite flight direction. The perpendicular baseline (Bp) is the distance B projected to a plane perpendicular to the line of sight (LoS), as illustrated in Figure 5. Generally, larger perpendicular baselines increase the sensitivity of the interferogram phase to topography, while smaller perpendicular baselines increase the sensitivity of the interferogram phase to deformations. Hence, for example, to measure ground movements, smaller baselines are preferred, but for DEM generation, larger baselines are better. However, the Bp cannot be too large, as the increase in Bp also reduces the phase coherency due to a larger difference in the

observation angles. When the B_p reaches the critical baseline (B_c), coherence between the satellite pair is totally lost, and interferometry is not possible. This is because a full phase cycle between adjacent resolution cells is reached, causing random phase from pixel to pixel rather than gradually varying values along the interferogram. Other factors, such as topography, influence the phase change along interferogram pixels, and therefore in practice the B_p should be notably smaller than the B_c .

Figure 5: InSAR geometry: B is the interferometric baseline, namely the distance between the satellite orbits, B_p is the perpendicular baseline, R is the range from the closer satellite to the ground, LoS is the line of sight direction, and θ is the incidence angle.

The B_c for flat earth can be calculated mathematically, as it is dependent on the SAR frequency (λ), distance to the target (R), incidence angle (θ) and slant range resolution (δr), such that:

$$B_c = \frac{\lambda R \tan \theta}{\delta r} \quad (1)$$

3.2.1 Method

Information about the B_p and the B_c , together with other metadata regarding the interferometric pairs, such as incidence angle, range from ellipsoid, bandwidth, and Doppler centroid, were extracted using the SNAP software. The Doppler centroid anomalies are discussed in section 3.3.

3.2.2 Results Compliance

The B_p , B_c , incidence angle, range from ellipsoid and bandwidth, are presented for the analysed Spot pairs in Table 2 and Strip pairs in Table 3. The last column shows whether the calculation of the interferometric coherence of the pair succeeded, and if yes, was the coherence considered good or bad (coherence is further discussed in section 3.4).

Table 2: The IDs of the primary and secondary scenes, perpendicular baseline (B_p), critical baseline (B_c), incidence angle, range from ellipsoid, range bandwidth, and the results of coherence calculation for the Spot stacks.

Stack	ID of Primary	ID of Secondary	B_p (m)	B_c (m)	Inc. Ang. (deg)	Range (m)	Rg. bandwidth (MHz)	Coh.
Spot 1	2450856	2450857	817	7378	21,5	605090	300	Error
	2480416	2490444	54	7314	21,3	604492	300	Error

Spot 2	2333586	2337462	2354	14694	21,2	610391	300	Error
	2337463	2348668	1445	17556	24,4	624822	300	Error
Spot 3	2516428	2516429	339	21117	28,2	635464	300	Error
	2845583	2856724	2539	15162	21,8	611712	300	Error
Spot 4	2352992	2360400	838	22462	29,4	644014	300	Error
	2401211	2408987	299	22218	29,2	642257	300	Error
Spot 5	2599461	2602530	284	26856	33,0	667015	300	Error
	2633501	2635330	532	26883	33,0	667679	300	Bad

Table 3: The IDs of the primary and secondary scenes, perpendicular baseline (Bp), critical baseline (Bc), incidence angle, range from ellipsoid, range bandwidth, and the results of coherence calculation for the Strip stacks.

Stack	ID of Primary	ID of Secondary	Bp (m)	Bc (m)	Inc. Ang. (deg)	Range (m)	Rg. bandwidth (MHz)	Coh.
Strip 1	2351485	2351486	516	2762	20,2	604461	178	Bad
	2351487	2351488	434	2844	20,8	605432	178	Bad
Strip 2	2440324	2448045	1202	3002	21,8	606597	166	Error
	2448046	2448047	151	3118	22,4	608769	166	Good
Strip 3	2490445	2507860	65	3960	26,6	636907	132	Bad
	2507861	2513263	130	4317	28,7	637236	132	Good
Strip 4	2568244	2581920	308	5069	31,9	657515	120	Error
	2599459	2599460	494	4492	29,4	644014	120	Bad
Strip Archive	58530	SM_58531	310	5572	34,0	667407	112	Bad
	59561	SM_59564	270	5555	33,8	668135	112	Bad

The Bp was typically few hundred meters, which is considered suitable for interferometry. In some cases, the Bp was exceptionally short or long, such as for the second pair of Spot 1 (54 m), the first pair of Strip 3 (65 m), the first pair of Spot 2 (2354 m), and the second pair of Spot 3 (2539 m). Nevertheless, the Bp was always considerably shorter than the Bc, meaning that interferometric applications are possible. If comparing the Bps with the coherence of the Strip pairs (Table 3), it seems like shorter baselines led to better coherences.

3.3 Doppler Centroid Difference

The radar beam records a range of Doppler frequencies. Objects in front of the satellite have a high Doppler frequency, while objects behind the satellite have a low Doppler frequency. Hence, the centre point, called the Doppler centroid (DC), can be used to find where the radar beam is pointing at any moment. In SAR interferometry, the best-case scenario would be equal DC frequencies in all resolution cells of the image pairs. However, due to satellite attitude variations, there is usually a small anomaly of the DC between the two images. As this anomaly increases, the reduced is the coherence between the images. According to ICEYE's documentation, ICEYE SAR images are zero-Doppler based, meaning that image pixels are always focussed to the zero-Doppler (broadside) position.

3.3.1 Method

The mean DC frequency difference for the image pair is calculated by the SNAP software.

3.3.2 Results Compliance

Information on the average DC anomaly and the azimuth bandwidth is shown for the Spot image pairs in Table 4 and Strip pairs in Table 5. The last column shows whether the calculation of the interferometric coherence of the pair succeeded, and if yes, was the coherence considered good or bad (coherence is further discussed in section 3.4).

Table 4: The IDs of the primary and secondary scenes, the average Doppler centroid (DC) anomaly, azimuth bandwidth, and the coherences of the Spot stacks.

Stack	ID of Primary	ID of Secondary	DC anomaly (Hz)	Az. bandwidth (kHz)	Coh.
Spot 1	2450856	2450857	21	30	Error
	2480416	2490444	-93	30	Error
Spot 2	2333586	2337462	851	30	Error
	2337463	2348668	666	30	Error
Spot 3	2516428	2516429	-188	30	Error
	2845583	2856724	-472	30	Error
Spot 4	2352992	2360400	-592	30	Error
	2401211	2408987	340	30	Error
Spot 5	2599461	2602530	111	30	Error
	2633501	2635330	-120	30	Bad

Table 5: The IDs of the primary and secondary scenes, the average Doppler centroid (DC) anomaly, azimuth bandwidth, and the coherences of the Strip stacks.

Stack	ID of Primary	ID of Secondary	DC anomaly (Hz)	Az. bandwidth (kHz)	Coh.
Strip 1	2351485	2351486	169	2.3	Bad
	2351487	2351488	-123	2.3	Bad
Strip 2	2440324	2448045	433	2.3	Error
	2448046	2448047	27	2.3	Good
Strip 3	2490445	2507860	33	2.3	Bad
	2507861	2513263	103	2.3	Good
Strip 4	2568244	2581920	-442	2.3	Error
	2599459	2599460	-178	2.3	Bad
Strip Archive	58530	58531	36	2.3	Bad
	59561	59564	-22	2.3	Bad

From the results in Table 4 and Table 5 we notice that there is a connection between the coherence results and the DC differences. The second pair of the Spot 5 stack was the only Spot pair where the coherence could be calculated, and it had a relatively small DC anomaly (120 Hz) compared to the other pairs. Only three pairs had a smaller DC difference. The same applies to the Strip pairs; the two pairs with “Good” coherence did not have large DC anomalies. Also, coherence could not be calculated for the pairs that had the largest DC anomalies (over 400 Hz). The DC anomaly is only one of the factors influencing successful interferogram formation, but based on our analysis, the DC anomalies of the test data had some impact on the ability to process the interferometric data. Most likely, smaller DC anomalies would have provided better quality results.

3.4 Coherence

The interferometric coherence determines the ability to derive interferometric products. It is calculated by sliding a sub-window over the image pair and calculating the correlation between the

measured phase of the two images. Zero coherence means no correlation between the two images, while a coherence value of one means perfect correlation between the phases. For natural targets, the coherence does not typically reach these extremes. Low coherence is usually considered below ~0.4, while high coherence above ~0.7. Random targets such as vegetation or sea surfaces have a low interferometric coherence, while stable targets such as rocky terrain have relatively high coherence. Due to low signal-to-noise ratio, low backscatter targets have a low coherence, even if they are stable, such as smooth paved surfaces.

3.4.1 Method

The interferometric pairs were first coregistered for attaining accurate geometric overlap between the images. For each pair, one primary and one secondary image were chosen, and the secondary image was geometrically fitted to the primary image. In many of the image pairs, mainly for the Spot data, the coregistration failed. For improving the coregistration results, we tried DEM assisted coregistration, with a high-resolution DEM. For this, a TanDEM-X DEM data with 12 m spatial resolution was obtained from DLR (German Aerospace Center) for the areas covered by the test datasets.

Different processing graphs for coregistration were considered in the analysis. We tested the coregistration and further coherence by trying different resampling methods, DEMs (besides the above described TanDEM-X DEM), sizes of windows for coregistration, and number of Ground Control Points (GCPs). However, there was no clear improvement in the results. Finally, the default values offered by SNAP were selected. We estimate that one of the reasons for the failure could have been large geometric shifts between the images.

3.4.2 Results Compliance

Table 6 presents the results of the coherence calculation for the X6 InSAR data. The results have been classified as “Good”, if the coherence was mostly around 0.6 and “Bad” if it was around 0.3. Pairs with “Bad” coherence had typically some areas where the coherence could not be calculated. “Error” was marked if the coregistration failed, or if the calculated coherence was close to zero.

Table 6: The results of the coherence calculation in SNAP. “Error” means that coherence could not be successfully computed. Coherence around 0.3 was considered as “Bad”, and coherence around 0.6 “Good”. The IDs of the SAR primary and secondary scenes is shown.

Stack	ID of Primary	ID of Secondary	Coh.
Spot 1	2450856	2450857	Error
	2480416	2490444	Error
Spot 2	2333586	2337462	Error
	2337463	2348668	Error
Spot 3	2516428	2516429	Error
	2845583	2856724	Error
Spot 4	2352992	2360400	Error
	2401211	2408987	Error
Spot 5	2599461	2602530	Error
	2633501	2635330	Bad
Strip 1	2351485	2351486	Bad
	2351487	2351488	Bad
Strip 2	2440324	2448045	Error
	2448046	2448047	Good
Strip 3	2490445	2507860	Bad

	2507861	2513263	Good
Strip 4	2568244	2581920	Error
	2599459	2599460	Bad
Strip Archive	58530	58531	Bad
	59561	59564	Bad

As shown in Table 6, the coherence was successfully retrieved only for one Spot pair, but the coherence was found to be bad. For the Strip data the results were better. Coherence was successfully calculated for most of the pairs. However, only for two pairs the calculated coherence was good. Figure 6 - Figure 10 show the coherence images on top of a Google Satellite background for pairs where the coherence was successfully calculated.

Figure 6: On the left, a Google Earth satellite view of the area, and on the right, on top of the same satellite view, the coherence between Spot 5 stack scenes 2633501 and 2635330 acquired on 4.9.2023 and 5.9.2023, respectively.

The Spot 5 stack was located over the Salar De Llullaillaco salt flat, Argentina. The top-right corner of the images shows man-made square-shaped lithium brine ponds, which based on the low coherence were most likely covered with liquids during the satellite imaging. The natural bright-coloured salt flats have a relatively high coherence compared to the hills inside the salt flat or soil surfaces around it. Yet, even the relatively high coherence salt flats show coherence values of only 0.3 at best, which is significantly less than what is expected for this kind of target.

Figure 7 shows the coherence of the archive Strip stack acquired over the borderline between Chile and Bolivia, near the town of San Pedro de Atacama, during June 2021. The area covered by the satellite acquisitions consists of mostly sandy or rocky flat and mountainous areas, and relatively small salt lakes or dry flats on the northern side of the images. In both pairs, the areas in the north-east and south-west parts of the images have higher coherence compared to the other areas. This is most likely due to the more flat and dry terrain. The Laguna Verde salt lake in the northern part appears as dark blue due to the water surface with low coherence. Albeit generally classified as “Bad” coherence, the second pair of the stack shows quite good coherence, even up to 0.6 in the dry and flat areas, and up to 0.7 in the dry channels that appear in the north-east part of the image. For some reason, the first pair shows generally somewhat lower coherence, maybe due to the 40 m longer Bp and the 14.1 Hz bigger DC anomaly.

Figure 7: On the top, a Google Earth satellite view of the area, and below, over the same satellite view, the coherence between the archive Strip scenes 58530 and 58531 acquired on 3.6.2021 and 4.6.2021 (left), and scenes 59561 and 59564 acquired on 5.6.2021 and 6.6.2021 (right).

Figure 8: On the top, a Google Earth satellite view of the area, and below, over the same satellite view, the coherence of the Strip 1 stack; between scenes 2351485 and 2351486 acquired on 16.7.2023 and 17.7.2023 (left), and between scenes 2351487 and 2351488 acquired on 19.7.2023 and 20.7.2023 (right).

Figure 8 shows the coherence of the two Strip pairs of stack 1 acquired around the Salar de Maricunga, that contains salty terrain and some water covered Lagoons. The surrounding area is mainly a mix of flat terrain with dry soil and rocky hills. The overall coherence in both analysed pairs was low. The best coherence could be reached over the mountain slopes in the north-west and western parts of the images, but even there, the coherence was only between 0.4 and 0.5 at best. Surprisingly, the whole salt flat in the middle had very low coherences, usually between 0.1 and 0.2. At least some of the area could have been under water cover, but most likely there were also exposed salt flats that should have had higher coherences. The coherence of the second pair seems to be slightly better than of the first one, maybe because it had 82 m shorter Bp and 46 Hz smaller DC anomaly compared to the first pair.

Figure 9: On the left, a Google Earth satellite view of the area, and on the right, on top of the same satellite view, the coherence of the Strip 2 stack; between scenes 2448046 and 2448047 acquired on 5.8.2023 and 6.8.2023.

Figure 9 shows the coherence of the second Strip pair of stack 2 acquired from the Salar de Pedernales salt flat, Chile. This salt flat is the largest one captured with the collected X6 stacks, located in the middle and southern parts of the image. The northern part of the images is mostly over the Dona Ines Mountain. In this stack the coherence of the first pair acquired at 2-3.8.2023 could not be retrieved. However, the second pair had relatively high coherence compared to the rest of the X6 pairs, with values reaching 0.7 over the salt flat of Salar de Pedernales.

Figure 10: On the top, a Google Earth satellite view of the area, and below, over the same satellite view, the coherence of the Strip 3 stack; between scenes 2490445 and 2507860 acquired on 14.8.2023 and 15.8.2023 (left), and between scenes 2507861 and 2513263 acquired on 17.8.2023 and 18.8.2023 (right).

Figure 10 shows the coherence of the two pairs from Strip 3 stack, acquired on the borderline between Chile and Argentina, over the salt flats of Salar de La Isla and Salar de las Parinas which are on the Chilean side of the border. The coherence of the second pair is notably higher than the coherence of the first pair. Over the Salar de La Isla, on the north-west part of the image, the coherence of the second pair reaches 0.8, while for the first pair it reaches 0.5. Here it can be clearly seen that the whitest regions of the salt flat, which assumingly contain the most salt, provide the best coherence. The Bp of the first and the second pairs are 65 m and 130 m, and the DC anomalies 33.3 Hz and 102.6 Hz, respectively. Hence, there should be some other explanation for the coherence differences between the pairs.

3.5 ICEYE's internal quality assessment

ICEYE performed an internal quality assessment for the same X6 interferometric pairs (Table 1) as the EDAP+ team, but by using the commercial SARPROZ software dedicated mainly for InSAR processing. As said, SARPROZ is the software recommended by ICEYE when processing their data for InSAR applications. This section provides a summary of the results of ICEYE's internal quality assessment, and a comparison with the results obtained by the EDAP+ team with the publicly available SNAP software.

Figure 11 - Figure 20 show the coherences obtained by ICEYE for all Spot and Strip interferometric pairs listed in Table 6. Figure 21 and Figure 22 show two examples of interferograms generated from the pairs, one for Spot and one for Strip. The coherence and interferogram maps shown in Figure 11 - Figure 22 are in the SAR measurement geometry, namely azimuth direction in the horizontal and range in the vertical axis.

Figure 11: Coherence calculated with SARPROZ for the first (left) and the second (right) Spot1 pairs.

Figure 12: Coherence calculated with SARPROZ for the first (left) and the second (right) Spot2 pairs.

Figure 13: Coherence calculated with SARPROZ for the first (left) and the second (right) Spot3 pairs.

Figure 14: Coherence calculated with SARPROZ for the first (left) and the second (right) Spot4 pairs.

Figure 15: Coherence calculated with SARPROZ for the first (left) and the second (right) Spot5 pairs.

Figure 16: Coherence calculated with SARPROZ for the first (up) and the second (down) Strip1 pairs.

Figure 17: Coherence calculated with SARPROZ for the first (up) and the second (down) Strip2 pairs.

Figure 18: Coherence calculated with SARPROZ for the first (up) and the second (down) Strip3 pairs.

Figure 19: Coherence calculated with SARPROZ for the first (up) and the second (down) Strip4 pairs.

Figure 20: Coherence calculated with SARPROZ for the first (up) and the second (down) Strip archive pairs.

Figure 21: Interferograms generated with SARPROZ for the first (left) and the second (right) Spot2 pairs.

Figure 22: Interferograms generated with SARPROZ for the first (up) and the second (down) Strip1 pairs.

In the results obtained by ICEYE with the SARPROZ software, the coherence was typically between 0.8 and 1 in the salt flats, and in most of the other stable targets, such as mountain slopes and the arid terrain. The obtained coherences are therefore according to expected values for these targets, and significantly higher compared to what was calculated for the same interferometric pairs in SNAP. The interferograms for all analysed pairs show mostly smooth and clear fringes, not only in the salt flats, but also in the mountainous terrain next to the flats. The interferograms therefore emphasize the successful InSAR results obtained by ICEYE.

For further comparing the coherences obtained with the SNAP and SARPROZ software, one example Spot pair and one Strip pair were chosen and presented in Figure 23 and Figure 24. The coherence calculated with SNAP is shown next to the coherence calculated with SARPROZ, after turning the SARPROZ images to the same orientation as the SNAP images, that are in the UTM map projection. The second pair of the Spot5 stack is presented, because this was the only Spot pair where a reasonable coherence was obtained with SNAP (Figure 23). The second pair of the Strip3 stack was chosen, because this was the most successfully processed pair with SNAP (Figure 24). The coherence in the salt flats is approximately 0.6 higher for the Spot pair and 0.3 higher for the Strip pair when processed with SARPROZ by ICEYE, compared to the ones processed with SNAP by the EDAP+ team.

Figure 23: The coherence calculated with SNAP (left) and SARPROZ (right) for the second pair of the Spot5 stack.

Figure 24: The coherence calculated with SNAP (left) and SARPROZ (right) for the second pair of the Strip3 stack.

4. DETAILED VALIDATION – SCANSAR

This chapter describes the assessment of the radiometric and geometric quality parameters performed by the EDAP+ team over the homogeneous and point target test areas, using test datasets of the Scan imaging mode from the X8, X12 and X13 satellites. The assessed radiometric quality parameters include the Noise Equivalent Sigma Zero (NESZ), Equivalent Number of Looks (ENL), Antenna Elevation Pattern (AEP) periodic image noise related to azimuth scalloping and inter-swath boundaries (ISB), and radiometric stability. The assessed geometric quality parameters include the spatial resolution, side lobes and geolocation accuracy, that are derived in the IRF-analysis.

4.1 Introduction

For evaluating the radiometric quality, data from homogeneous and low backscatter areas were collected. Rainforests are considered a stable and homogeneous target with relatively low dependency of the measured backscatter on imaging angle, due to the influence of the dense forest canopies. Therefore, rainforests are ideal for assessing the calibration with respect to the antenna elevation angle, namely AEP, and the radiometric stability between different scenes. Rainforest images were requested from the Amazonas, specifically from areas covered with thick forest canopy, excluding e.g. large rivers, villages, or forest cuts. Glaciers are also considered homogeneous targets for SAR, and they are used in our analysis for the assessment of the ENL. In previous EDAP assessments of X-band SAR data, glaciers were found more suitable for assessing the ENL than rainforests. Glacier scenes for the analysis were collected from Antarctica.

The Ocean Doldrums zone as well as smooth desert surfaces cause low backscatter, due to specular reflection of the radar signal on the smooth surfaces and high penetration in the dry desert sand. Scenes from the low backscatter targets of the Atlantic Doldrums and the Sahara and Arab Peninsula Deserts are therefore used in our analysis to assess the NESZ. The Desert images are also used for assessing the ENL, because of the chosen homogeneous desert surfaces. Table 7 lists the test areas used for the radiometric evaluation, and which quality parameters were assessed in each area. Figure 25 shows the areas where the Doldrums, Rainforest and Desert scenes were collected.

Table 7: The radiometric quality parameters assessed for each test area.

Test Area	NESZ	ENL	AEP	Stability
Rainforest			X	X
Glacier		X		
Doldrums	X			
Desert	X	X		

Figure 25: Test areas of Atlantic Doldrums (upper right), Amazonas Rainforest (left) and Desert (bottom) from which the data were collected.

Table 8, Table 9 and Table 10 list the test areas, product ID numbers, acquisition dates, average incidence angles, and processor version numbers of the ICEYE Scan scenes used by the evaluation team for the assessment of the radiometric data quality within the EDAP+ activity, for X8, X12 and X13 satellites, respectively.

Table 8: X8 data products included in the assessment of the radiometric quality parameters, provided by ICEYE to the EDAP+ team.

Test Area	ID number	Date	Incidence Angle	Processor version	
Low backscatter	Doldrums	2273644	2023-07-02	28.2	1.90
		2273645	2023-07-03	27.4	1.90
		2277170	2023-07-03	28.6	1.90
		2307559	2023-07-07	27.1	1.91
		2307560	2023-07-08	29.2	1.91
		2307561	2023-07-08	29.2	1.91
	Desert	2154670	2023-05-12	28.6	1.88
		2158739	2023-05-20	28.6	1.88
2252867		2023-06-18	28.4	1.89	
Homogeneous areas	Rainforest	2154436	2023-05-13	19.8	1.88
		2154437	2023-05-17	24.9	1.88
		2154438	2023-05-18	22.8	1.88
		2154439	2023-05-13	28.7	1.88
		2154440	2023-05-14	28.6	1.88
		2154441	2023-05-18	28.4	1.88
		2258406	2023-06-26	19.2	1.90
		2258407	2023-06-26	29.2	1.90

	Glacier	2273656	2023-07-01	18.1	1.90
		2273657	2023-07-01	22.3	1.90
		2273658	2023-07-01	28.3	1.90

Table 9: X12 data products included in the assessment of the radiometric quality parameters, provided by ICEYE to the EDAP+ team.

Test Area		ID number	Date	Incidence Angle	Processor version	
Low backscatter	Doldrums	2271799	2023-07-01	27.9	1.90	
		2274205	2023-07-01	28.5	1.90	
		2274206	2023-07-01	28.2	1.90	
		2274207	2023-07-02	28.4	1.90	
		2274208	2023-07-02	28.1	1.90	
		2274209	2023-07-03	28.8	1.90	
Low backscatter	Desert	2154597	2023-05-13	28.1	1.88	
		2154598	2023-05-17	28.6	1.88	
		2258146	2023-06-24	28.4	1.90	
Homogeneous areas	Rainforest	2154488	2023-05-14	19.7	1.88	
		2154499	2023-05-15	28.7	1.88	
		2157602	2023-05-18	19.5	1.88	
		2157603	2023-05-19	22.6	1.88	
		2159149	2023-05-20	28.4	1.88	
		2178480	2023-05-25	27.8	1.88	
		2268590	2023-06-26	28.9	1.90	
		2271793	2023-06-29	18.5	1.90	
	Homogeneous areas	Glacier	2274214	2023-07-01	22.5	1.90
			2274215	2023-07-01	28.3	1.90
			2318480	2023-07-11	18.2	1.91

Table 10: X13 data products included in the assessment of the radiometric quality parameters, provided by ICEYE to the EDAP+ team.

Test Area		ID number	Date	Incidence Angle	Processor version	
Low backscatter	Doldrums	2273650	2023-07-01	28.7	1.90	
		2273651	2023-07-01	26.2	1.90	
		2273652	2023-07-02	28.5	1.90	
		2276266	2023-07-03	28.3	1.90	
		2276267	2023-07-03	28.7	1.90	
		2286763	2023-07-04	28.7	1.90	
Low backscatter	Desert	2154624	2023-05-16	28.5	1.88	
		2154625	2023-05-18	28.8	1.88	
		2252784	2023-06-16	28.7	1.89	
Homogeneous areas	Rainforest	2154534	2023-05-13	19.6	1.88	
		2154535	2023-05-14	20.7	1.88	
		2154536	2023-05-17	21.4	1.88	
		2154538	2023-05-13	28.8	1.88	
		2154539	2023-05-17	28.2	1.88	
		2154541	2023-05-12	28.0	1.88	
		2252761	2023-06-17	20.8	1.89	
		2268520	2023-06-27	29.6	1.90	
	Homogeneous areas	Glacier	2273661	2023-07-02	27.8	1.90
			2295040	2023-07-07	18.2	1.91
2315858			2023-07-07	18.5	1.91	

For evaluating the geometric data quality, IRF analyses are performed over the Rosamond Corner Reflector Array located near the south beach of Rosamond Dry Lakebed in California. The site is managed by NASA's Jet Propulsion Laboratory (JPL) and contains trihedral corner reflectors (CRs), providing quality values for spatial resolution, geolocation accuracy, and the power

distribution of the measured radar beam (PSLR and ISLR). The installed CRs have face widths of 4.8 m, 2.4 m, and 0.7 m (Figure 26). All large (4.8 m) and small (0.7 m) reflectors are directed towards east, and approximately half of the medium size (2.4 m) are directed towards east and half towards west. All possible overpassing orbits were utilized, namely both right and left looking acquisitions of the ascending and descending orbits, providing that the incidence angle over the site was over 21 degrees.

Figure 26: A Google Earth view of the Rosamond CR site in California. The smaller image in the upper right side shows the surrounding area of the site. The bottom image is a closer view on the CR site, showing the CR names, alignment, and distribution at the site.

Table 11 lists the product ID number, acquisition date, orbit direction, look direction, average incidence angle, and processor version number of the ICEYE Scan scenes used in the evaluation of the geometric quality parameters for X8, X12 and X13 satellites.

Table 11: X11 data products included in the assessment of the IRF quality parameters, provided by ICEYE to the EDAP+ team.

Satellite	ID number	Date	Orbit	Look direction	Inc. angle	Proc. version
X8	2165298	2023-05-20	Desc	Left	22.6	1.88
	2165299	2023-05-21	Desc	Right	24.3	1.88
	2180916	2023-05-25	Asc	Left	32.4	1.88
	2180917	2023-05-25	Desc	Left	31.0	1.88
	2181740	2023-05-29	Asc	Right	20.2	1.88
	2200260	2023-05-30	Asc	Left	25.0	1.88
	2200261	2023-06-03	Asc	Right	28.1	1.89
	2252345	2023-06-21	Desc	Right	32.2	1.97
	2273640	2023-06-26	Desc	Right	31.3	1.97
	2307551	2023-07-01	Desc	Right	31.5	1.97
	2372802	2023-07-23	Asc	Right	29.2	1.91

	2391739	2023-07-28	Asc	Right	21.9	1.91
	2391740	2023-07-29	Asc	Left	26.6	1.91
X12	2165261	2023-05-16	Desc	Left	28.8	1.97
	2165262	2023-05-22	Asc	Left	23.1	1.88
	2178486	2023-05-24	Desc	Right	31.1	1.97
	2180107	2023-05-27	Asc	Right	24.0	1.88
	2181734	2023-05-30	Desc	Right	21.9	1.88
	2200511	2023-06-04	Desc	Left	23.6	1.89
	2209696	2023-06-10	Desc	Left	30.3	1.89
	2227690	2023-06-16	Asc	Left	28.6	1.89
	2275171	2023-06-28	Asc	Left	24.6	1.90
	2308941	2023-07-10	Asc	Left	27.5	1.91
	2351496	2023-07-16	Desc	Left	31.3	1.97
	2368351	2023-07-22	Desc	Left	25.3	1.97
	2397921	2023-07-29	Desc	Right	23.4	1.91
X13	2165283	2023-05-19	Desc	Left	21.3	1.88
	2178208	2023-05-25	Desc	Left	21.9	1.97
	2184970	2023-05-31	Desc	Left	20.1	1.97
	2200877	2023-06-04	Asc	Right	32.0	1.89
	2209347	2023-06-07	Desc	Right	22.1	1.89
	2209348	2023-06-10	Asc	Right	27.9	1.89
	2226716	2023-06-13	Desc	Right	27.6	1.89
	2228542	2023-06-16	Asc	Right	22.2	1.89
	2257843	2023-06-23	Asc	Left	25.9	1.90
	2272472	2023-06-29	Desc	Left	25.9	1.97
	2367620	2023-07-20	Asc	Right	29.0	1.91
	2389875	2023-07-27	Asc	Left	32.2	1.91
	2389876	2023-07-27	Desc	Left	29.3	1.91

The SQT developed by Aresys was used for assessing the radiometric and geometric quality metrics. The measured quality values were evaluated by comparing them with the corresponding quality values stated in the ICEYE documentation. The evaluation results are considered good if the measured quality parameters are better or similar than the values provided by ICEYE. On the contrary, the quality is considered weak if the measured quality parameters are worse than the provided values in the documents. In case there were not any defined values for a certain quality parameter in the ICEYE documentation, the grading was decided based on commonly known values typical to X-band SAR sensors.

Several received products had initially a weaker quality than what is presented in this document. The weaknesses were mostly related to their localization accuracy because they were processed by ICEYE using the “rapid” orbit fidelity level. After a request by the EDAP+ team, these data were inspected and reprocessed by ICEYE using the “precise” orbit fidelity, which usually improved their quality.

4.2 Equivalent Number of Looks (ENL)

The equivalent number of looks (ENL) indicates the degree of averaging applied to the SAR measurements during data generation and postprocessing. Hence, for multilook (averaged) images, such as the GRD data products, the ENL should be the number of observations used for calculating one representative backscatter value, while for single look images, such as the SLC data products, the ENL should be one.

4.2.1 Method

The ENL analysis is typically performed over natural distributed homogeneous targets. In this analysis the test areas used for the assessment were in the Antarctica Glacier. All test data sets were GRD products where the number of looks accounted in azimuth and range directions is one,

meaning that the ENL should be close to one. Traditionally the ENL has been assessed using data from rainforests as well. However, in previous assessments of X-band SAR data we found, that the ENL of rainforests is typically notably below the ideal value of one for SLC data. This happens most likely because rainforests are not homogeneous enough regarding the X-band SAR. In the current analysis of the Scan data for X8, X12 and X13 satellites, the ENL over rainforest was also notably lower than one, namely around 0.6-0.9. The analysis was performed using the SQT software, by manually selecting five homogeneous sub-areas over the scene and calculating the ENL over them.

4.2.2 Results Compliance

Table 12 show the median and the std of the measured ENL in Glacier.

Table 12: ENL results for the Antarctica Glacier.

Satellite	Scene ID	Median	Std
X8	2273656	0.99	0.02
	2273657	1.00	0.00
	2273658	0.97	0.01
X12	2274214	0.98	0.01
	2274215	0.96	0.02
	2318480	0.97	0.02
X13	2273661	0.98	0.01
	2295040	0.96	0.02
	2315858	0.99	0.01

The measured ENL for the analysed ICEYE data from the Antarctica was usually very close to the ideal value of ENL=1. The maximum deviation from 1 was up to 0.04. Hence, based on the ENL analysis over the Antarctica Glacier, the results show correct radiometric signatures of the ICEYE Scan data.

4.3 Antenna Elevation Pattern (AEP)

The observed SAR backscatter needs to be corrected for changes caused by the antenna elevation angle in the range direction. A pre-defined antenna elevation pattern (AEP) is used by the data provider for compensating the contribution of the elevation angle to the measured gain. In this section we assessed whether the AEP correction was applied correctly on the ICEYE Scan data.

4.3.1 Method

The images were analysed by averaging the backscatter in azimuth direction and extracting range profiles of the averaged backscatter in ground range units at five different points along the azimuth direction, as indicated by the narrow red boxes of Figure 27. The backscatter profiles were then normalized by the inverse of the average measured backscatter, and a second-order polynomial was fitted to the profiles. The analysis was performed on the Rainforest scenes, where the noise component can be considered negligible (very low) compared to the target backscatter level. Gamma nought (γ^0) backscatter was chosen because it is independent of the incidence angle with the ground surface. Ideally, the normalized γ^0 range profiles should be horizontal, with a value of zero dB along the whole x-axis.

Figure 27: Illustration of the AEP assessment method with the X8 Scan image 2154439 from the Amazonas Rainforest in the background. Gamma nought (γ^0) backscatter profiles in range direction were extracted at five different points along the azimuth direction, marked with red boxes in the image. The backscatter was averaged in azimuth direction for deriving a range profile line.

4.3.2 Results Compliance

The normalized AEP with respect to the ground range distance extracted from the analysed SAR Scan images are shown in Figure 28 for X8, Figure 29 for X12 and Figure 30 for X13. In all figures, plots on the left side are from the scenes acquired with $\sim 20^\circ$ incidence angle, and the plots on the right side from the scenes with $\sim 30^\circ$ incidence angle.

Figure 28: AEP profiles of X8 Scan scenes from the Amazonas. Acquisitions having $\sim 20^\circ$ incidence angle are on the left side and acquisitions with $\sim 30^\circ$ on the right side.

Figure 29: AEP profiles of X12 Scan scenes from the Amazonas. Acquisitions having $\sim 20^\circ$ incidence angle are on the left side and acquisitions with $\sim 30^\circ$ on the right side.

Figure 30: AEP profiles of X13 Scan scenes from the Amazonas. Acquisitions having $\sim 20^\circ$ incidence angle are on the left side and acquisitions with $\sim 30^\circ$ on the right side.

Generally, the AEP correction performed by the data provider did not result in horizontal range profiles. There was no clear dominant trend in the profile shapes, meaning that there were many increasing and decreasing, as well as parabolic shape profiles. The parabolic shape of the profiles may be caused by image speckle effects, thus it is not necessarily related to the AEP correction performance. However, the increasing or decreasing trends between near and far range are most likely related of the changing antenna elevation angle.

The change between near and far range was typically around 2 dB, and up to 4 dB. Only in two out of the analysed 24 scenes the profiles could be considered as stable and flat, with less than 1 dB bias from the horizontal zero-line along the near to far range. The scenes acquired at around 30° incidence angle showed somewhat better range profiles compared to the ones with $\sim 20^\circ$ angle. There were no clear differences in the quality of the AEP correction between the three analysed satellites. The AEP correction performed by the data provider to the Scan data can be therefore considered basic.

The results presented here for the Scan acquisition mode are less successful from the results obtained with the Strip and Spot modes in previous analyses [RD-5]. This is expected, as the variation in elevation angles is significantly larger in Scan compared to Strip and Spot modes, and therefore the compensation of the effect of elevation angle is more challenging.

4.4 Noise Equivalent Sigma Zero (NESZ)

One of the most essential quality indicators in SAR is the noise equivalent sigma zero (NESZ), showing the contribution of noise in the observed backscatter. Weaker NESZ is an indication of higher quality SAR data, because targets with relatively low backscatter can be identified with less noise disturbance. The NESZ is typically assessed in calm water surfaces or dry and smooth desert areas due to their low backscatter.

4.4.1 Method

The NESZ is assessed here using images acquired during July over the Atlantic Doldrums summer zone, presumably with calm and flat sea surfaces, and over selected smooth and dry surfaces in Sahara and the Arab Peninsula (Figure 25) deserts during May-June. To minimize the observed backscatter, data with the shallowest (highest) possible incidence angle were chosen, namely around 30 degrees incidence angle. Data are analysed with the SQT by manually extracting and plotting radiometric profiles of the sigma nought (σ^0) backscatter in range direction from low backscatter areas. The range profiles are calculated at five different points along the azimuth direction, in a similar manner than in the AEP analysis (Figure 27), and the representative NESZ is considered the average σ^0 at the minimum of these profiles along the range direction. Since there may be some residual backscatter even in the selected relatively low backscatter areas, the minimum of the range profile graph showing the lowest backscatter can be considered the NESZ value, assuming that the contribution of the target itself to the observed backscatter power is negligible.

Figure 31 shows an example of range profiles extracted from two Scan scenes from the Atlantic Doldrum zone. The Scan scenes have a wide footprint, and therefore in all scenes there were also higher backscatter areas present in the imaged area. It was usually challenging to find locations where the whole profile along the range direction was from low-backscatter areas. Also, as the whole image contains four beams, an ideal profile would have four parabolas next to each other, each parabola representing one collected beam. The examples of Figure 31 demonstrate the challenge of finding dark backscatter profiles, and the presence of beams in the scenes.

Figure 31: Range profiles of two example scenes with the matching quicklook images. The profile and image on the upper row are from the scene 2274205 from X12, and on the lower row from scene 2273644 from X8.

4.4.2 Results Compliance

The NESZ provided in the ICEYE documentation for the Scan products is between -22.2 and -21.5 dB. Table 13 list the measured NESZ values for the analysed data in the Doldrums, and Table 14 in Desert. As said, the values in the tables are the lowest calculated average values of the radiometric profiles.

Table 13. Measured NESZ of the X8, X12 and X13 Scan scenes for the Atlantic Doldrums.

ID	Satellite	NESZ (dB)
2273644	X8	-25,51
2273645	X8	-13,10
2277170	X8	-19,82
2307559	X8	-15,81
2307560	X8	-20,47
2307561	X8	-16,4
2271799	X12	-22,37
2274205	X12	-23,84
2274206	X12	-19,54
2274207	X12	-26,54

2274208	X12	-21,28
2274209	X12	-17,08
2273650	X13	-17,14
2273651	X13	-23,47
2273652	X13	-23,37
2276266	X13	-20,54
2276267	X13	-21,86
2286763	X13	-14,99

Table 14. Measured NESZ of the X8, X12 and X13 Scan scenes for the Desert areas.

ID	Satellite	NESZ (dB)
2154670	X8	-20,05
2158739	X8	-21,47
2252867	X8	-23,75
2258146	X12	-23,49
2154597	X12	-21,66
2154598	X12	-23,31
2252784	X13	-22,23
2154624	X13	-18,85
2154625	X13	-20,7

In Figure 32 the measured NESZ level of the analysed Scan X8, X12 and X13 data is depicted with red, blue and green horizontal lines, respectively. As a reference, the NESZ provided in the ICEYE documentation is depicted with grey horizontal line.

Figure 32: Horizontal lines showing the measured NESZ of the analysed Scan data, with a grey line representing the reference NESZ provided in ICEYE's documentation. Update image

In the Doldrums area the NESZ was many times higher than the expected level of -22.2 to -21.5 dB. This is probably caused by wavy water in the imaged area. Even though the target areas were inside the July Doldrums zone, the water surface was not always calm. In Figure 33 some example images of wavy and calm water surfaces are shown.

Figure 33: Examples of Doldrum wavy water surfaces on the upper row; scene 2273645 from X8 and scene 2286763 from X13, and calm water surfaces on the lower row; scene 2273644 from X8 and scene 2274207 from X12.

In the Desert images the NESZ is generally closer to the expected values, with three images showing somewhat stronger, and three images somewhat weaker NESZ than expected.

The measured stronger NESZ in some of the images can be partly caused by an overestimation due to the method used in the SQT. When calculating the σ^0 range profiles, all pixels in the azimuth direction are averaged, rather than choosing only the low backscatter pixels in the averaging. In contrary, the methodology used by ICEYE for calculating the NESZ ignores the higher backscatter pixels of the sample and therefore the calculated NESZ is lower. The methodology applied by ICEYE is documented in RD-6.

Another possible reason for the relatively high observed NESZ in some of the images is the difficulty in finding areas with very low backscatter. This is because the analysis is performed on co-polarization data and not on cross-polarization, the shallowest possible incidence angle offered by ICEYE is 30° , and the imaged surfaces are often not ideally flat. Even though the sea surface images were collected from the Doldrums zone, some winds can still be present in the imaged areas causing wavy water which increases the observed backscatter. The selected relatively smooth desert surfaces may also contain some wavy terrain or rocks and thus reflect back some of the SAR signal.

4.5 Azimuth Scalloping and Inter-Swath Artifacts

In the Scan imaging mode of the analysed ICEYE satellites, for capturing a wider imaged area, steering of the satellite's phased array antenna is performed to scan four adjacent strips (swaths/beams) in elevation direction. The boundaries between the adjacent swaths can have sudden shifts in the backscatter intensity, also known as inter-swath boundary (ISB) artifacts. The Terrain Observation by Progressive Scans (TOPS or TOPSAR) technique in which the antenna is steered sideways during each burst is used for avoiding these ISB artifacts and resulting in homogeneous image quality along the range direction. On the other hand, the antenna steering may cause periodic noise in the azimuth direction separating adjacent bursts, namely azimuth scalloping.

4.5.1 Method

The method for assessing the azimuth scalloping and ISB artifacts was based on visual inspection of the backscatter images from the Rainforest and Glacier sites, where the target is homogeneous along the whole imaged area, and the noise component can be considered negligible (very low) compared to the target backscatter level. In addition, the range profiles shown in section 4.3.2 (Figure 28 - Figure 30) from Rainforest were utilized for identifying ISB artifacts in range direction. The backscatter images and the range profiles were visually analysed for finding possible periodic noise and backscatter shifts along the azimuth direction (scalloping) and along the range direction (ISB).

Figure 34: Steering of the phased array satellite antenna is performed to obtain the Scan images. Figure copied from ICEYE's interactive documentation.

4.5.2 Results Compliance

Based on visual inspection of the backscatter images, quite strong azimuth scalloping artifacts were present on most of the Glacier images, and ISB artifacts were usually visible on those images, although they were not as strong as the scalloping artifacts. In the Rainforest images, less scalloping artifacts were observed, and the observed ones were generally weaker compared to the Glacier images. ISB artifacts were not present in most of the Rainforest images, but in a few cases, they appeared strongly, such as in the 2154440 and 2258407 images of X8 and 2154535 image of X13. For the Glacier images, the quality was similar for all satellites, but for the Rainforest images, more artifacts were present in the X8 images, and the least in the X13 images. Table 15 lists the images where azimuth scalloping and/or ISB artifacts were observed, classifying them as weak, strong or very strong. Examples of backscatter images with relatively strong observed scalloping or ISB effects are shown in Figure 35 for the Rainforest images and in Figure 36 for Glacier.

Table 15: The observed periodic artifacts of the SAR backscatter images in range and azimuth directions. The artifacts in range direction are caused by inter-swath boundaries between the four scanned swaths in elevation, and the artifacts in azimuth direction are due to boundaries between the bursts of the same swath.

Satellite	ID Number	ISB artifacts	Scalloping
Rainforest			
X8	2154437	weak	no
	2154438	weak	strong
	2154439	weak	weak
	2154440	very strong	weak
	2258406	weak	weak
	2258407	strong	strong
X12	2154488	weak	weak
	2159149	weak	weak
	2268590	weak	weak
X13	2154535	strong	weak
	2154541	weak	weak
Glacier			
X8	2273656	weak	strong
	2273657	no	weak
	2273658	weak	strong
X12	2274214	weak	weak
	2318480	no	strong
X13	2273661	weak	strong
	2295040	weak	strong
	2315858	no	weak

Figure 35: Examples of Rainforest backscatter images with observed scalloping and ISB artifacts. Top left: 2154438 of X8, top right: 2154440 of X8, bottom left: 2258407 of X8 and bottom right: 2154535 of X13.

Figure 36: Examples of Glacier backscatter images with observed scalloping and ISB artifacts. Top left: 2273656 of X8, top right: 2273658 of X8, bottom left: 2318480 of X12 and bottom right: 2295040 of X13.

As said, ICEYE applies the TOPSAR technique to avoid the ISB artifacts, and indeed these are usually not present in the image data. Only in a few images there were clear shifts of backscatter between collected swaths, and sometimes these ISB lines were noticed more due to the azimuth scalloping effect that separates between the bursts, and thus reveal the border lines between the swaths. Azimuth scalloping noise was more frequently observed, especially in the Glacier images, but also in some Rainforest images. ICEYE is currently not performing radiometric corrections for compensating the scalloping noise. Hence, it is expected that these scalloping artifacts can exist in the image data. Based on our data analysis and relative to the corrections applied or not applied by ICEYE, we can therefore conclude that the quality of the Scan data in terms of scalloping and ISB noise is good. However, users should consider that as long as radiometric correction of scalloping is not performed, these artifacts can appear in the data.

4.6 Radiometric Stability

The radiometric stability and consistency reflect the ability of the satellite measurements to repeatedly produce similar calibrated backscatter values from targets having the same properties and conditions. Better radiometric stability thus enables the users to correctly analyse and interpret

multiple observations acquired at different times or from different locations having the same target properties.

4.6.1 Method

The radiometric stability of SAR is usually tested over rainforests, because they result in a spatially homogeneous backscatter with small seasonal changes and low dependency on incidence angle. For assessing the radiometric stability, all acquired data from the Amazonas Rainforest are analysed. Radiometric range profiles calculated with σ^0 as output at five representative points along the azimuth direction (as in the AEP analysis, Figure 27). An average of all samples was calculated for each SAR scene using the linear power units, and the result was converted to decibel values. The standard deviation was calculated directly from the decibel values.

4.6.2 Results Compliance

The absolute radiometric accuracy (within one data scene and over time) derived during the commissioning phases by ICEYE was 2 dB RMSE (RD-9). The relative radiometric accuracy, indicating the standard deviation of the observations within one data scene is defined as 1 dB. The average and the standard deviation for each analysed scene are presented in Figure 37.

Figure 37: Average and standard deviation of the Sigma Nought backscatter for the Amazonas Rainforest Scan Scenes.

The backscatter was typically between -8.5 and -6.5 dB, but in 9 out of the 24 analysed scenes, the backscatter was notably weaker, namely between -14 and -9 dB. The standard deviation within the scenes was usually between 1 to 2 dB, with few exceptions of larger variability, up to 3 dB. All analysed satellites presented similar radiometric stability. If excluding the 9 exceptional scenes, the radiometric stability could be considered good. However, 9 scenes represent more than two thirds of the total analysed data, and therefore, generally, based on our assessment, the radiometric stability is considered basic.

4.7 Spatial Resolution and Side Lobes

The spatial resolution and the strength of the side lobes with respect to the main lobe determine the ability of the SAR data to distinguish objects on the image. The spatial resolution is defined as the width of the main lobe in range and azimuth at a level of 3 dB below the maximum of the main lobe, as marked by the red dashed horizontal lines in Figure 38. The peak side lobe ratio (PSLR) represents the relation between the closest side lobes (to the main lobe) and the main lobe, while

the integrated side lobe (ISLR) the relation between all relevant side lobes and the main lobe. Hence, the narrower is the main lobe and the smaller are the side lobes, the better is the ability of the SAR data to distinguish smaller objects in the image from the surrounding area.

4.7.1 Method

The distribution of the measured power from the reflectors and the area around the reflectors are analysed, providing the spatial resolution of the SAR data and the power of the secondary lobes relative to the main lobe (PSLR and ISLR). The individual CRs are first located automatically by the SQT or by manually selecting specific CRs, and the IRF parameters are then calculated by the software for the included CRs. Figure 38 shows an example of the spatial distribution of the measured power from one of the CRs in Rosamond and the obtained results for the spatial resolution, PSLR and ISLR.

Figure 38: Assessment of the spatial resolution, PSLR and ISLR with the SQT. An example showing the main and the side lobes for the Scan scene 2227690 acquired with the X12 satellite over Rosamond.

4.7.2 Results Compliance

Table 16 shows the quality values related to the spatial resolution and the side lobes provided in the ICEYE online interactive product documentation (checked 04/2024). The spatial resolution is given in ground range direction for the assessed GRD data. A single quality value is provided by ICEYE for each imaging mode. A value for the ISLR is not currently provided by ICEYE in the public documentation. In an old version of the Product Guide an ISLR of approximately -4.4 dB was defined by ICEYE, but in the more recent analyses performed by ICEYE for the Strip and Spot imaging modes of the X11-X13 satellites, the measured ISLR was mostly between -12 and -9 dB. Therefore, the reference ISLR concerning the EDAP+ evaluation activity is defined in Table 16 as between -12 and -4.4 dB.

Table 16: Quality values related to the IRF analysis, provided in the ICEYE documentation.

Product type	Range resolution [m]	Azimuth resolution [m]	PSLR [dB]	ISLR [dB]
Scan	15	15	-20	-12...-4.4

Table 17, Table 18 and Table 19 show the results of the measured spatial resolution, PSLR and ISLR for the analysed satellites X8, X12 and X13, respectively. The values presented in these tables are plotted for spatial resolution in Figure 39, for PSLR in Figure 40, and for ISLR in Figure 41. The spatial resolution in range and azimuth directions was always better than the values provided in the ICEYE documentation, typically between 8 and 8.5 m in range and between 13.5 and 14 m in azimuth. The PSLR in azimuth was usually weaker than -20 dB, meaning somewhat better than the defined value, but in range direction the PSLR was significantly stronger than expected, typically around -8 dB. Similarly, the ISLR in azimuth was usually weaker than -15 dB, but in range between -5 and -3 dB. Hence, generally the side lobes measured in azimuth direction were within or better than the expected values, but in range direction the side lobes can be considered very strong, and concerning PSLR, significantly stronger than the expected strength. Even though the ISLR for range was very strong, it remained mostly according to defined value of -4.4 dB stated in the old ICEYE documentation. All analysed satellites had similar performance concerning the spatial resolution and side lobes.

It should be noted that compared to other available spaceborne X-band SAR data, the spatial resolution of the ICEYE products is very good, while the side lobes are relatively strong. This is because in the product processing, a windowing function is not applied. A windowing function, such as Taylor, Hanning, Hamming or Kaiser, which is often applied in SAR processing, reduces the side lobes while also reducing the spatial resolution of the data. Generally, based on our assessment described above, the spatial resolution of the ICEYE X11-X13 data can be considered excellent, and the side lobes can be considered moderate.

Table 17: IRF spatial resolution and side lobes for X8

Im. ID	Resolution (Rg) [m]	Resolution (Az) [m]	PSLR (Rg) [dB]	PSLR (Az) [dB]	ISLR (Rg) [dB]	ISLR (Az) [dB]
2165298	7,66 ± 0,52	13,15 ± 0,72	-7,33 ± 0,69	-19,56 ± 2,23	-1,96 ± 1,35	-15,49 ± 3,05
2165299	8,34 ± 0,91	13,62 ± 0,86	-8,24 ± 1,38	-20,24 ± 3,05	-3,87 ± 2,73	-16,16 ± 3,57
2180916	8,45 ± 0,88	13,4 ± 0,83	-8,59 ± 1,32	-21,41 ± 1,72	-4,13 ± 2,52	-17,25 ± 1,91
2180917	8,78 ± 0,91	14,17 ± 0,84	-8,84 ± 1,48	-20,56 ± 2,73	-4,92 ± 2,51	-16,93 ± 3,08
2181740	8,53 ± 0,97	13,41 ± 0,69	-8,73 ± 1,73	-20,97 ± 2,55	-4,38 ± 2,72	-17,25 ± 1,94
2200260	8,69 ± 0,88	14,02 ± 0,79	-8,67 ± 1,34	-20,82 ± 2,68	-4,71 ± 2,42	-16,66 ± 2,87
2200261	8,33 ± 0,81	13,6 ± 0,61	-8,27 ± 1,13	-20,95 ± 3,24	-3,81 ± 2,34	-17,35 ± 3,16
2252345	8,61 ± 0,72	13,34 ± 1,11	-8,54 ± 0,98	-21,75 ± 2,29	-4,52 ± 2,1	-17,58 ± 1,57
2273640	8,5 ± 0,6	13,94 ± 0,72	-8,4 ± 0,42	-22,25 ± 2,36	-4,06 ± 1,44	-18,66 ± 2,81
2307551	8,29 ± 0,83	13,81 ± 0,88	-8,6 ± 1,37	-23,78 ± 3,04	-3,84 ± 2,57	-19,93 ± 2,89
2372802	8,23 ± 0,96	13,83 ± 0,68	-8,2 ± 1,47	-20,38 ± 3,22	-3,51 ± 2,72	-16,73 ± 3,05
2391739	8,19 ± 0,94	12,93 ± 0,71	-8,09 ± 1,47	-21,7 ± 2,34	-3,38 ± 2,55	-17,17 ± 2,49
2391740	8,8 ± 0,69	13,5 ± 0,82	-8,71 ± 1,37	-22,55 ± 2,47	-5,05 ± 2,19	-18,45 ± 2,05

Table 18: IRF spatial resolution and side lobes for X12

Im. ID	Resolution (Rg) [m]	Resolution (Az) [m]	PSLR (Rg) [dB]	PSLR (Az) [dB]	ISLR (Rg) [dB]	ISLR (Az) [dB]
2165261	7,93 ± 0,41	13,07 ± 0,52	-7,53 ± 0,4	-20,4 ± 2,41	-2,62 ± 1,02	-16,5 ± 2,54
2165262	7,95 ± 0,79	14,01 ± 0,9	-7,79 ± 1,1	-19,95 ± 5,38	-2,78 ± 2,28	-16,58 ± 4,13
2178486	8,65 ± 0,96	13,4 ± 0,81	-8,88 ± 1,7	-20,65 ± 3,65	-4,55 ± 2,48	-16,63 ± 3,56
2180107	8,26 ± 0,9	13,86 ± 0,66	-8,39 ± 1,65	-21,24 ± 1,91	-3,68 ± 2,74	-17,31 ± 2,94
2181734	8,32 ± 1,04	13,72 ± 0,79	-8,32 ± 1,64	-19,55 ± 3,53	-3,41 ± 2,46	-15,37 ± 3,81
2200511	8,39 ± 0,9	13,61 ± 0,71	-8,35 ± 1,43	-18,52 ± 3,54	-3,89 ± 2,56	-14,61 ± 4,21
2209696	8,42 ± 0,75	13,59 ± 0,9	-8,48 ± 0,73	-19,66 ± 2,98	-3,86 ± 2,11	-15 ± 3,08
2227690	8,27 ± 0,75	13,64 ± 0,65	-8,17 ± 1,3	-23,32 ± 3,49	-3,64 ± 2,19	-19,29 ± 3,11
2275171	8,32 ± 0,95	13,85 ± 0,7	-8,41 ± 1,86	-21 ± 2,58	-3,88 ± 2,87	-17,61 ± 3,17
2308941	8,37 ± 0,71	13,91 ± 0,74	-8,17 ± 0,88	-21,77 ± 6,05	-3,98 ± 2,03	-18,54 ± 4,99
2351496	8,68 ± 0,99	13,79 ± 0,58	-8,71 ± 1,48	-19,54 ± 2,51	-4,48 ± 2,46	-14,81 ± 2,67
2368351	7,95 ± 0,76	13,51 ± 0,66	-7,69 ± 1,12	-21,41 ± 2,56	-2,77 ± 2,07	-17,99 ± 3,24
2397921	7,86 ± 0,4	13,47 ± 0,9	-7,47 ± 0,42	-21,68 ± 2,6	-2,5 ± 1,01	-17,62 ± 1,86

Table 19: IRF spatial resolution and side lobes for X13

Im. ID	Resolution (Rg) [m]	Resolution (Az) [m]	PSLR (Rg) [dB]	PSLR (Az) [dB]	ISLR (Rg) [dB]	ISLR (Az) [dB]
2165283	8,08 ± 1,01	13,34 ± 0,81	-8 ± 1,71	-18,8 ± 3,75	-2,98 ± 2,72	-14,22 ± 4,6
2178208	8,39 ± 1,14	13,45 ± 0,87	-8,68 ± 2,19	-18,53 ± 4,61	-3,73 ± 2,88	-13,58 ± 4,67
2184970	8,6 ± 0,91	13,72 ± 0,9	-8,87 ± 1,45	-18,66 ± 3,66	-4,02 ± 2	-14,39 ± 4,69
2200877	8,26 ± 0,75	13,3 ± 0,76	-8,62 ± 0,84	-20,78 ± 4,72	-3,66 ± 2,23	-16,82 ± 4,23
2209347	7,79 ± 0,61	13,79 ± 0,59	-7,43 ± 0,84	-21,37 ± 2,63	-2,27 ± 1,53	-17,46 ± 2,29
2209348	9,03 ± 0,96	14,17 ± 0,61	-9,33 ± 1,71	-20,1 ± 1,96	-5,81 ± 2,8	-16,4 ± 2,78
2226716	8,71 ± 0,78	13,59 ± 0,79	-8,75 ± 0,85	-22,12 ± 3,31	-4,86 ± 2,16	-18,83 ± 3,38
2228542	8,52 ± 0,94	13,63 ± 0,65	-8,63 ± 1,68	-21,23 ± 2,4	-4,32 ± 2,69	-16,8 ± 1,41
2257843	8,34 ± 0,98	13,55 ± 0,67	-8,36 ± 1,55	-21,95 ± 1,62	-3,99 ± 2,97	-18,13 ± 2,54
2272472	7,98 ± 0,85	13,86 ± 1,02	-7,71 ± 1,23	-19,98 ± 3,4	-2,82 ± 2,29	-16,62 ± 2,99
2367620	8,1 ± 0,83	13,99 ± 0,88	-8,14 ± 1,12	-20,24 ± 3,65	-3,16 ± 2,22	-16,76 ± 3,63
2389875	8,73 ± 0,86	13,47 ± 0,84	-8,86 ± 1,39	-21,56 ± 1,32	-4,99 ± 2,57	-17,29 ± 1,53
2389876	8,1 ± 0,6	13,8 ± 0,95	-7,8 ± 0,69	-20,58 ± 3,98	-2,95 ± 1,53	-16,14 ± 5,49

Figure 39: The average and standard deviation of the measured spatial resolution for the identified CRs in each of the analysed scenes of X8, X12 and X13 satellites.

Figure 40: The average and standard deviation of the measured PSLR for the identified CRs in each of the analysed scenes of X8, X12 and X13 satellites.

Figure 41: The average and standard deviation of the measured ISLR for the identified CRs in each of the analysed scenes of X8, X12 and X13 satellites.

4.8 Geolocation Accuracy

4.8.1 Method

The IRF analysis typically includes a calculation of the localization error in a SAR scene. The given locations of bright targets (CRs) are compared with the locations of the CRs on the SAR image. The localization error is expressed in both azimuth and range directions. Figure 42 presents an example of localization accuracy analysis for one CR over Rosamond with the the Scan scene 2200877 of the X13 satellite. The red dot is the expected location of the reflector on the SAR image, based on the geographical coordinates of the reflector (e.g. the true location). The green plus (+) sign shows the location of the same reflector on the SAR image, detected by the software based on the backscatter distribution.

Figure 42. Geolocation accuracy assessment with the SQT. The expected point target (red dot) location is compared with the location on the observed SAR image (green plus sign). The example above is from the scene 2200877 acquired with the X13 satellite over Rosamond.

4.8.2 Results Compliance

A localization error of 15 m RMSE is provided in the ICEYE online interactive product documentation for the Scan imaging mode. Table 20, Table 21 and Table 22 show the results of the localization error analysis performed over Rosamond for the X8, X12 and X13 satellites, respectively. The average and standard deviation of the errors for all identified CRs in each scene is provided in the first two columns, and the absolute localization error (ALE) calculated from the averages in the third column. The lowest row shows the RMSE of the average localization errors in range, azimuth and ALE. In Figure 43 the localization errors are plotted in a range-azimuth plane, together with a circle showing the expected localization error of 15 m RMSE. The range error is provided in ground range, and the ALE is the circular error calculated from the errors in azimuth and ground range.

According to the results, there was a notable difference in the performance of X8 compared to X12 and X13 satellites. X8 had an ALE localization error of 12.3 m RMSE, which is better than the value provided by ICEYE, but X12 and X13 had errors of close to 19 m RMSE, namely a few meters larger than expected. For X8 the errors were usually larger in range than in azimuth, while for X12 and X13 the errors were larger in azimuth. Hence, overall, the geolocation errors of the data can be considered somewhat larger than the value provided in the documentation. However, if considering only the results of X8, the localization accuracy would have been very good.

Table 20: IRF localization accuracy for X8

Im. ID	Range error [m]	Azimuth error [m]	ALE [m]
2165298	3,71 ± 1,75	-0,34 ± 0,78	3,73
2165299	-12,24 ± 2,75	0,8 ± 0,94	12,27
2180916	-19,89 ± 2,84	-12,26 ± 1,11	23,36
2180917	17,98 ± 0,68	3,86 ± 0,96	18,39
2181740	17,45 ± 2,77	3,72 ± 1,06	17,84
2200260	-18,8 ± 3,61	-4,31 ± 0,83	19,29
2200261	-4,93 ± 0,63	4,37 ± 0,78	6,59
2252345	-2,25 ± 2,92	-1,95 ± 4,08	2,98
2273640	-4,58 ± 0,66	4,64 ± 0,61	6,52
2307551	-1,96 ± 2,58	2,08 ± 4,68	2,86
2372802	-3,34 ± 3,16	0,96 ± 3,58	3,48
2391739	10,01 ± 2,77	0,24 ± 0,5	10,01
2391740	1,87 ± 2,02	-0,38 ± 0,52	1,91
Total (RMSE)	11,47	4,37	12,27

Table 21: IRF localization accuracy for X12

Im. ID	Range error [m]	Azimuth error [m]	ALE [m]
2165261	4,18 ± 3,48	-12,62 ± 4,42	13,29
2165262	19,22 ± 1,19	-14,12 ± 3,15	23,85
2178486	5,18 ± 0,63	-9,59 ± 2,68	10,90
2180107	-14,96 ± 1,83	-19,33 ± 0,87	24,44
2181734	12,58 ± 3,25	-15,65 ± 1,24	20,08
2200511	4,08 ± 2,01	-19,4 ± 4,09	19,82
2209696	-5,71 ± 1,39	-17,59 ± 2,94	18,49
2227690	-1,93 ± 3,17	-21,72 ± 6,2	21,81
2275171	-0,86 ± 3,12	-18,09 ± 1,36	18,11
2308941	-0,46 ± 0,73	-24,11 ± 3,66	24,11
2351496	-2,23 ± 2,38	-17,59 ± 2,99	17,73
2368351	10,12 ± 1,12	-7,99 ± 2,89	12,89
2397921	-0,72 ± 1,51	-14,54 ± 0,59	14,56
Total (RMSE)	8,58	16,92	18,97

Table 22: IRF localization accuracy for X13

Im. ID	Range error [m]	Azimuth error [m]	ALE [m]
2165283	-4,92 ± 3,08	-13,47 ± 0,87	14,34

2178208	11,03 ± 4,06	-12,06 ± 1,25	16,34
2184970	1,46 ± 4,24	-12,08 ± 0,97	12,17
2200877	-6,43 ± 0,55	-23,1 ± 4,53	23,98
2209347	0,64 ± 3,7	-17,93 ± 1,64	17,94
2209348	-1,81 ± 3,66	-22,1 ± 5,81	22,17
2226716	-3,51 ± 3,36	-18,32 ± 4,44	18,65
2228542	-0,78 ± 4,75	-19,52 ± 1,86	19,54
2257843	-3,28 ± 1,2	-17,7 ± 0,72	18,00
2272472	3,88 ± 1,4	-22,23 ± 4,32	22,57
2367620	-3,89 ± 2,76	-19,31 ± 4,17	19,70
2389875	-3,75 ± 0,54	-17,29 ± 3,72	17,69
2389876	0,14 ± 2	-23,12 ± 3,38	23,12
Total (RMSE)	4,48	18,70	19,23

Figure 43: Average localization errors calculated from all identified CRs in range and azimuth directions for the analysed X8, X12 and X13 scenes, and the expected localization error (RMSE).